

Multi-Camera Human Pose Estimation for Minimal Distance Monitoring in Industrial Robot Cells

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Abstract. The proliferation of robots in shared human environments demands robust safety in human–robot collaboration. In this article, the authors propose a Minimal-Distance Monitoring system aimed at augmenting safety within industrial robotic cells. It adopts a decentralized, multi-camera perception system to achieve precise, real-time pose estimation of human operators throughout the shared workspace. By fusing sensory inputs from heterogeneous viewpoints, the system enhances spatial perception, mitigates occlusion effects, and ensures robust detection of human postural configurations. Continuous computation of the minimal distance between the human model and robot’s links enables risk assessment during human-robot collaboration operations. This persistent monitoring mechanism not only enforces safety compliance but also facilitates the optimization of collaborative robotic workflows in contemporary industrial automation contexts.

Keywords: minimal distance monitoring, speed and separation monitoring, robot safety, human-robot collaboration, human pose estimation

1 Introduction

The rapid evolution of manufacturing automation within the Industry 4.0 framework has accelerated the adoption of human-robot collaboration (HRC), enabling high-volume production and flexible customization by combining human intelligence, adaptability, and situational awareness with robotic precision, endurance, and repeatability, thereby leveraging the complementary strengths of both to improve operational efficiency across a range of industrial tasks such as assembly, welding, inspection, and material handling. A key component of this integration is Speed and Separation Monitoring (SSM), one of the four collaborative operation modes defined in ISO 10218 and ISO/TS 15066, which continuously monitors the position and motion of humans and adjusts robot speed to maintain a prescribed minimum separation distance, using sensing technologies to define safety zones that may be static or dynamically adapted based on relative motion, even though the standard does not prescribe detailed implementation methods.

This research extends the work of Grajeda *et al.* [3] in the European Union’s Horizon Europe SMARTHANDLE project, which developed a multi-view 3D human pose estimation system using edge computing. This article presents a Minimal-Distance Monitoring (MDM) system based on the previous work to enhance safety in industrial robotic cells. Furthermore, the recent refinements made to that perception system are also detailed here.

The core concept of this approach consists in monitoring the real-time separation distances between robots and humans rather than static regions in space. Two safety distances are predefined as distance thresholds that correspond to distinct robot behaviors: a reduced-speed distance and a protective stop distance, which determine the robot response when an operator approaches it. The system integrates data from a multi-camera system using YOLOv8 [14] as pose estimator, uses Flexible Collision Library (FCL) [12] to compute distances between robots and humans, and is built on ROS 2 [8] for real-time, distributed communication and reading robot’s joints positions. Consequently, the system enhances safety compliance and optimizes human-robot collaborative workflows in modern industrial automation settings.

2 Related Work

To provide context for our methodology, we first present a concise overview of pertinent research efforts undertaken by other researchers in recent years.

A considerable body of research has explored this topic in the last decade, with numerous survey and review papers offering comprehensive overviews of recent advances in HRC, MDM and SSM [4] [5] [15] [7]. With respect to perception systems, it is common to employ Microsoft Kinect V2 [13] [6] [9] that intrinsically yields the skeletal representation of the detected humans; to that end, regular cameras are also used combined with YOLO models to track people [1] [2]; as well as other devices like RealSense [16]. The Flexible Collision Library (FCL) [12] is commonly used [13] [6] for distance computation, collision detection, and continuous collision checking; or the Kinematic Continuous Collision Detection (KCCD) library as an alternative [10].

3 Method

In this section, the technicalities of the system are described, including perception, human pose estimation, robot’s position acquisition, virtual representation of the different elements in the cell (robots and humans), distance calculation and robot’s speed override.

3.1 Decentralized Image Acquisition

To enable a robust multi-view 3D human pose estimation in complex workspaces, we employ a decentralized image acquisition system composed of multiple cameras mounted on fixed positions and oriented towards the region of interest. Each

camera is connected to a dedicated edge device responsible for image acquisition, processing, and pose inference tasks. The image acquisition module compresses the raw image data locally before processing it with the pose inference module. This architecture eliminates the need of sending large images to a central computer, reducing bandwidth requirements.

3.2 Calibration

The multi-camera system requires two types of calibration: intrinsic and extrinsic calibration, both performed using OpenCV. This process involves capturing multiple images of a calibration target, such as a checkerboard pattern. Intrinsic calibration is carried out to determine the internal parameters of each camera and to reduce lens distortion, ensuring accurate image measurements. Extrinsic calibration is then used to estimate the position and orientation of each camera with respect to the robot’s coordinate system, enabling proper spatial alignment and 3D reconstruction.

3.3 Virtual Representation of Humans

Decentralized 2D Human Pose Estimation. The 2D human pose estimation module runs inference on the acquired images with a YOLOv8-pose model. If a human is detected, a pose P with 17 keypoints is generated. Each keypoint corresponds to a joint or key feature in the human body.

Each estimated pose P is checked for quality with three conditions. First, the score of each keypoint is compared against a threshold to quantify the number of low confidence keypoints. If too many keypoints show a low score, P is discarded. In second place, the overall score of P is validated by averaging the scores of every keypoint. If the overall score is below a predefined threshold, P is not accepted. Lastly, it is checked if the estimated pose is within the bounds of a predefined region. If all of these checks are successful, the pose is considered valid and sent to the central computer to be processed for 3D human pose estimation. A visual representation of the four possible outcomes is shown in Figure 1.

Centralized 3D Human Pose Estimation. To establish correspondence between 2D human poses from different camera views, a pairwise 2D pose matching is performed between all devices. For each camera pair $C(i, j)$, each 2D pose k from device i , P_k^i , is compared to every 2D pose l from device j , P_l^j .

The geometric relationship between each camera pair is defined by their fundamental matrix F_{ij} , which has been calculated from the calibration results. Epipolar geometry is applied to evaluate spatial consistency between the corresponding keypoints in each possible pose pair. This is done by calculating the perpendicular distance from each joint keypoint m in P_k^i to the epipolar line from the joint keypoint m in P_l^j . These distances are aggregated in a cost matrix built to contain the information of all possible pose pairs in $C(i, j)$.

Fig. 1. Showcase of the four possible outcomes for a detected pose.

The Hungarian algorithm [11] is used to determine the optimal pose correspondences from the cost matrix. This yields the global optimal match that minimizes the sum of the geometric distance between poses. Pose pairs with a matching cost below a predefined threshold are accepted as valid. From each accepted pair of poses (P_k^i, P_l^j) , the resulting 3D pose \mathbf{P} is triangulated using known camera projection matrices \mathcal{P}_i and \mathcal{P}_j . This process is repeated for every possible camera pair $C(i, j)$, and the resulting 3D poses are appended to a list of candidate poses.

Statistical Human Pose Matching. Due to overlapping detections from different pairs of cameras, the same individual may be reconstructed multiple times as separate pose instances, as seen in Figure 2(a). To ensure that each person in the scene is only represented by a single consistent 3D pose, we implement a statistical pose comparison and refinement procedure to identify redundant poses and merge them into a unified representation, as shown in Figure 2(b).

The aforementioned process is described in detail in the lines that follow. Given a candidate triangulated pose \mathbf{P}_i and an already accepted pose \mathbf{P}_j , a Student's t-test is performed to assess whether they correspond to the same subject or not. This test is performed on the distributions of their 3D joint coordinates. The null hypothesis assumes that both poses represent the same human in the real world. If the absolute value of the resulting t-statistic satisfies

$|t| < threshold$, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and both poses are considered statistically similar. In this case, \mathbf{P}_i is considered a duplicate of \mathbf{P}_j .

Human Pose Refinement Strategies. If two poses represent the same person, their keypoints are processed using one of several refinement methods to merge both representations. Each method provides a different balance in the fusion of redundant detections.

- a) **Average Fusion.** The resulting joint coordinates are obtained from the average of the corresponding keypoints of both poses. For every 3D joint coordinates \mathbf{p} of keypoint k , Eq. 1 is applied:

$$\mathbf{p}_k = \frac{\mathbf{P}_k^i + \mathbf{P}_k^j}{2}, \quad s_k = \frac{s_k^i + s_k^j}{2} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{p}_k^i and \mathbf{p}_k^j represent the 3D position vectors of the k -th keypoint for poses i and j . Similarly, s_k^i and s_k^j denote the confidence scores of the k -th keypoint of each pose.

- b) **Weighted Average Fusion.** The keypoint coordinates are weighted by their confidence score to build the resulting joint, as shown in Eq. 2:

$$\mathbf{p}_k = \frac{\mathbf{p}_k^i s_k^i + \mathbf{p}_k^j s_k^j}{s_k^i + s_k^j}, \quad s_k = \frac{(s_k^i)^2 + (s_k^j)^2}{s_k^i + s_k^j} \quad (2)$$

This method emphasizes detections with higher confidence while preserving information from both sources.

- c) **Best Pose Selection.** The overall confidence of each pose is determined as shown in Eq. 3:

$$S_i = \sum_k s_k^i \quad (3)$$

The existing pose is replaced by the candidate pose if $S_i > S_j$.

- d) **Best Keypoint Selection.** A keypoint-wise comparison is executed, as defined in Eq. 4:

$$\mathbf{p}_k = \begin{cases} \mathbf{p}_k^i, & \text{if } s_k^i > s_k^j \\ \mathbf{p}_k^j, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The joint of the existing pose is replaced by the joint of the candidate pose if $s_k^i > s_k^j$.

- e) **First Pose Retention.** The first pose is retained. Any subsequent duplicate detections are ignored.

The selection of the pose refinement strategy to use can be selected by the user according to the strategy that better suits its needs.

Once this step is completed, the system has a 3D representation for each detected human in our workspace. Figure 2 displays all initial 3D human poses and the result of filtering for a single frame.

Fig. 2. Side by side comparison of the effects of pose filtering using weighted averages.

Human Virtual Model. To perform distance computations against the robot’s virtual model, humans are represented through a simplified geometric model composed of one cylinder that adjusts its position and dimensions according to the pose keypoints (Figure 3). Then, those cylinders are created as BVH-based (Bounding Volume Hierarchy) solid models allowing FCL to perform efficient distance computations.

Fig. 3. Virtual human representation as cylinder for distance calculation purposes.

3.4 Virtual Representation of Robots

In ROS 2, the `robot_state_publisher` is a fundamental node that transforms a robot’s joint state information into a complete kinematic representation by publishing TF2 transforms. It operates by reading the robot’s kinematic model, which is typically defined in a Unified Robot Description Format (URDF) file,

and by subscribing to the `/joint_states` topic. This topic provides real-time data on joint positions. The node then uses this information to perform forward kinematics and compute the spatial relationships between all links in the robot. Afterwards, it broadcasts these transformations on the `/tf` and `/tf_static` topics. This allows other ROS 2 components to accurately interpret the robot's geometry and movement in space, as seen in Figures 2, 3 and 4.

In the present work, each link of the robot corresponds to a solid model generated via BVH representation. FCL employs BVH-based models to execute geometric computations and distance calculation between robot components and the virtual human models (cylinders).

Fig. 4. Original CAD of the robot (in gray) vs. downsampled model (in green)

3.5 Minimal Distance Calculation

An algorithm implements a brute-force pairwise distance calculation by evaluating the minimal distance function for every combination of robot links and human cylinders, using FCL and BVH models. The nested iteration structure ensures complete coverage of all possible link-human pairs, storing intermediate results in a vector before extracting the global minimum distance. The minimum distance is evaluated against two predefined thresholds (T_{stop} and T_{slow}) that determine whether the robot should stop or reduce its speed.

This approach guarantees correctness by full checking, while leveraging FCL's optimized distance computations. If the current pairwise distance is below T_{stop} , the loop breaks, allowing early termination to save processing time and memory.

The implementation of a window filter is imperative for effective signal processing, thereby accentuating the most restrictive values. This speed override signal is then transmitted to the robot through a communication interface defined by the robot's manufacturer.

4 Experimental Results

Processing Performance. Compared to our previous implementation in Grajeda *et al.* [3], the improvements reflect an increase in throughput in both acquired frames per second and pose inference speed, as shown in Table 1. Image acquisition enhancements reflect a 39.3% increase in fps with respect to our previous 22 fps. Regarding pose estimation, an increase of 40.2% has been observed from our previous benchmark of 19 fps. Both, previous and current, results have been measured while running the complete inference pipeline in a Jetson Orin Nano and the same YOLOv8l-pose model with an input size of 512x320.

Table 1. Throughput Performance

Module	Previous (<i>fps</i>)	Current (<i>fps</i>)	Improvement
Image Acquisition	~ 22.0	30.65	39.3%
Pose Estimation	~ 19.0	26.64	40.2%

3D Pose Error. By placing a human joint at known 3D points, the accuracy of the system was measured by comparing the ground truth coordinates and the reconstructed 3D joint coordinates. We assume that the pose errors obtained in the tests significantly represent the distribution of our system as $X \sim \mathcal{N}(5.5, 3.6^2)$, in cm. In the context of our application, this translates to a 3% variability in the size of an average person.

Minimum Distance Calculation. This algorithm demonstrates that performance improves as the number of triangles in the robot’s model decreases, since fewer computations are required for processing the distances (Table 2). Therefore, down-sampling the CAD models of the robot (Figure 4) is important to reduce geometric complexity and enhance processing speed. Hardware also significantly impacts performance since modern processors with greater computational capacity are capable of executing processes with high efficiency. Therefore, reducing the number of triangles and using a modern processor can effectively achieve real-time performance.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This research has addressed the issues identified in our previous implementation, improving throughput in our edge devices and overall performance. Additionally, key improvements have been implemented in the 2D human pose estimation stage to filter out noisy poses that brought instabilities to the 3D reconstructions.

Table 2. Minimal Distance Calculation Algorithm Performance

Processor	Number of triangles	Time (<i>ms</i>)
Intel Xeon Gold 6252	69187	~ 85.0
Intel Xeon Gold 6252	96	~ 1.4
Intel Core i9-13900HK	69187	~ 0.3
Intel Core i9-13900HK	96	~ 0.08

Our new statistical comparison between 3D poses is significantly more reliant than the previous distance-based approach, and has improved the detection of redundant poses while simplifying the parameterization required for the setup of our system. Besides, the implemented pose refinement strategies allow for proper handling of redundant poses according to use-case-specific needs. In conjunction, both of these improvements provide increased robustness and flexibility to our multi-view 3D human pose estimation system.

The results achieved in terms of calculating the minimum distance have also been very satisfactory. The system sends the appropriate override signal to the robot in each situation in an optimal manner and in real time.

As for future work, the major focus of our research in human pose estimation is to implement the temporal identification of entities across frames. Improvements in safety calculations involve implementing dynamic speed distances based on the robot’s speed, according to the formulas that appear in ISO/TS 15066.

Acknowledgement

This research was partly funded by the SMARTHANDLE project, which received funding from the European Union’s research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101091792.

This research activity has been co-funded by the CASANDRA project PLEC2024-011064, which is funded by MICI/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by FEDER, UE.

Authors’ Contributions

Alejandro Grajeda: Software Development, Integration and Testing of Human Tracking; Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing. **Claudio Sánchez:** Software Development, Integration and Testing of MDM and SSM; Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing. **Isidro Fernandez:** Project Management, Hardware Integration, Resources, Review. **David Castro:** Supervision and Conceptualization of Human Tracking; Review. **Jawad Masood:** Supervision; Conceptualization; Review.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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